

**LIBERATION OF WOMEN IN A POST-GLOBALIZED
WORLD: A TRANSNATIONAL STUDY OF MARJAN
KAMALI'S *LION WOMEN OF TEHRAN***

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Abstract

The rights of women have consistently been violated, and they struggle hard for their existence and identity. These women have to resist the patriarchal and authoritative structure. This research examines the rights of women in Tehran on a global scale. The aims and objectives of this research are to explore how the novel becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in a post-globalized world. It also discusses how women are uniting globally against this oppression. It explores how women resist the power dynamics that marginalized them. The approach used for this research is qualitative, as no numerical data or surveys are used. The primary source of this research is the textual study of *Lion women of Tehran*, and the secondary data include all articles, quotes, and papers that support this research with textual evidence. This research analyzes the data using a research question approach. The research describes the suffering and struggles of women for their rights and existence at a broader level. In a world where women's voices were silenced, the characters' friendship became a beacon of hope and resistance. This research challenges the patriarchal norms and power dynamics that tried to oppress and marginalize women with resilience and strong determination.

Keywords: *Authoritative, Dehumanization, Discrimination, Equality, Feminist, Gender Rights, Oppression, Patriarchy, Resistance, Resilience, Subjugation*

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1. Introduction

Lion women of Tehran (2024) by Marjan Kamali is set against the backdrop of the Iranian revolution, and women struggle for rights. This is a true representation of feminism, power dynamics, friendship, and loyalty. This further explores class inequality, betrayal, guilt, and redemption, and especially focuses on culture and tradition, which is depicted in a great way. It describes the Iranian political landscape and its effects on people, especially on women. This novel is set against the significant historical events in Iran, including the coup e'er eta, the rise of the Shah, and the subsequent Islamic and Iranian Revolution. It mainly portrayed the complexities and harsh experiences of Iranian women. It shows their struggle for existence and for basic rights of vote, education, marriage, custody of children, employment, and the right to divorce.

The harsh picture of power dynamics and true identity is beautifully represented through culture and especially food. The selected fiction raises the voices of Iranian women who are struggling with bravery against patriarchal and authoritative structures. The selected fiction represents the story of two friends, their friendship, and how these friends considered themselves as SHIR ZAN and how the political turmoil and class differences turned the lives of characters. In a world where women's voices were silenced, the characters' friendship became a beacon of hope and resistance. This novel is rich with the knowledge of Iranian culture, tradition, and all these things have vivid sensory details to bring the setting to life with immersion in the sounds, foods, and smells of Tehran and New York.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Iranians have always tried to marginalize and oppress the people. They tried to get control through power dynamics. The people of Tehran suffer from an Identity crisis, dehumanization, and marginalization, especially women. Women have to face several challenges and struggle hard for their right to vote, marriage, education, employment, and even for children's custody, and for their very existence. The novel *Lion women of Tehran* by Kamali discusses the rights of women and their resistance against the powers that tried to marginalize them. The novel's characters similarly describe the harsh experience of Iranian women, the Impact of historical events on women's lives, and how it reshapes their Identities. This research is going to explore women's rights at a broader level. It describes the issues that these women have to face in Tehran, but their migration also affects their Identity. So, the marginalization of their rights is not only at the local level, but broadly in the whole world. Women are facing difficulties and challenges, and exploring the transnational struggle of their identity and existence.

1.2. Research Objectives

The aims and objectives of this research are;

- To explore how the novel becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in a post-globalized world.
- To explore how women are being unified against this oppression on a global scale.
- To determine how women resist against the power dynamics that marginalized them.

1.3. Research Questions

1. How the novel becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in a post-globalized world.
2. How women are being unified against this oppression on a global scale.
3. How do women resist against the power dynamics that marginalized them.

1.4. Research Significance

The rights of women have always been violated, and they struggle hard for their existence and identity. In regard to this, *Lion women of Tehran* portrays the resilience of Iranian women and their inner psyches developed across generations. These psyches are shaped by class discrimination and power dynamics. The novel further describes the life experiences of women in the aftermath of the Iranian revolution, which has a great impact on their lives. Previous research has explored the struggle for women's identity within the premises of Iran, but this research fills the gap by analyzing Kamali's novel by placing women in a post-globalized world and exploring a transnational struggle of their identity. But this research has explored a new lens of transnational feminism. This describes the struggle for the rights of women not at a local level, but according to the global context of hybridity and cultural discussion. It also describes how women's identities and trauma are shaped by migration, exile, and displacement. It has set a new lens and angle for the coming generations to watch and explore the *Lion women of Tehran* in a broader way. This theory sets a new lens for the coming generation to see that the lives of women of Tehran cannot be understood through a national lens; it helps to examine the flow of power, culture, and the resistance for rights across borders.

2. Literature Review

Georgiano (2025) mainly describes the harsh experiences and struggles of women against the social, political, and cultural oppression in a patriarchal society before and after the revolution in *Lion Women of Tehran*. The characters' lives and their friendship are greatly affected by class differences and political turmoil, which leads to their separation. It describes the struggle of women for their basic rights, including education, marriage, employment, and children's custody. It describes their struggle to get their own identity, which was oppressed by the authoritative structure. The novel is analyzed by Silvy Walby's Patriarchal structure, which describes household production, state, male violence, objectification of women, and cultural institutions. It shows women's resistance against this patriarchal structure and male dominance through protests and rejection of norms, and

they tried to live their lives according to their will. Through the character of Ellie and Homa, they tried to set an example and a beacon of hope and friendship, which encourages women who are facing dehumanization across generations and are able to unify the women against oppression across the world. The selected fiction shows that literature is seen as a tool to show women's resistance against political and societal suppression, which marginalizes them across history. It describes women's struggles in a transnational, diasporic, and colonial context (Georgiano, 2025).

Mafakhir (2016) which shows Sometimes the tradition and culture are used to exploit and dehumanize women, as *The Holy Women* (2001) presented about the character Zarri Bano, which shows the exploitation because her brother was dead and she had to marry according to the Holy Quran, which is known as the Shehzadi Ibadat tradition. She wants to get married to his beloved, but due to inheritance issues, she would not be able to do so. She struggles hard in order to avoid all these circumstances, which have deeply changed her identity and the basic right of marriage. Due to this tradition and for the family honour, she silently became a toy for the male-dominated society and was treated as an object. Zarri Bano has to resist this tradition and marry her beloved person, but she would not be able to escape from the patriarchy created by her father and grandfather, and is forced to follow the tradition. The character's life lacks happiness and smiles, and the suppression of their rights leads to harsh experiences in life. All these events lead to inner conflict, which badly affects their life. This was a great lesson for women to fight for their rights and not follow these types of traditions because women have equal rights. Women are allowed to live their lives according to their will (Mafakhir, 2016).

Mu'arrof (2016) in this research, the novel explores the life of Mukhtar Mai, who does domestic work and her husband has to work in the fields in order to fulfill their requirements and basic needs. She was raped, and according to the law, she has to present four witnesses in order to prove it. She was dehumanized by the police and through society. The novel describes the male dominance and the exploitation of women, especially of the character who was dragged and then raped. All these events clearly describe women seen as objects and being objectified and only considered for male satisfaction. All these events have badly affected their psyche and led to inner conflict. Women are not allowed to get an education and are not allowed to speak in family matters. Even the police and law are not able to give them their basic rights, and mothers prayed for sons, not daughters. Mukhtar Mai has to struggle hard against the patriarchal and authoritative institution. But she resisted these circumstances with bravery and opened a school in order to give education to women who are considered illiterate, and they showed protest against a society Who put limits on women. This novel describes how women have to speak for their rights (Mu'arrof, 2016).

Luzae, Setijowati & Afdholy (2023) through this article the novel *Woman at Point Zero* (1975) portrayed a woman who became a prostitute because she did not like men who use slave women for their sexual satisfaction. Firdaus has lost her hope in God and does not want to become an object for men because women are being objectified and muted, and are not allowed to speak for their rights. The character becomes a prostitute and sells herself at a price. Through this profession, the character tried to get the confidence that was lost while becoming a slave. From day one, the rights of women are not considered. These women are suppressed in a male-dominant society and are not able to gain the respect and identity that they deserve. These women are considered objects and dehumanized, and all these events have a great impact on their physical and psychological health. These events led them to inner conflict and had a bad effect on their psyche, and they tried to regain their identity and confidence AS Firdaus became a prostitute just to give herself importance and to regain her confidence. Through this research, we would be able to understand that women should be given equal importance and rights (Luzae, Setijowati & Afdholy, 2023).

Zahra (2024) in her research describes about the characters' struggle against patriarchy in Meg Ellison's *The Book of Flora* (2019). Ellison describes the structures of patriarchy portrayed in *The Book of Flora*, and it describes women's struggle against the authoritative structure. Firstly, it describes how Dinty is sold by her father, and secondly, it describes the dehumanization of characters like Dinty, Flora, and Etta from male dominance. Then Flora is seen as an object of male satisfaction and is being objectified, and it also suggests that the state supports men and sets limits for women. It describes their unification against these authoritative structures, as Flora searches for her mother. So, she can buy herself and other characters to fight against the male violence to protect them. In order to escape from the state, they went to a place where these women live their lives according to their will. In the selected fiction, *The Book of Flora* portrays women's struggles and their unification against society. This research describes the novel in a patriarchal theory, but it also helps to see through this novel with a different lens and helps to focus on the women's struggle and their resistance against society for their basic rights and for their existence in this society (Zahra, 2024).

Sinta & Ambalegin (2020) which elaborates the rights of women who always been violated, and they struggle hard for their existence and identity. In regard to this, *Romeo and Juliet* (1597) also describe the circumstances that were faced by women. The novel's character Juliet lives in a patriarchal society where women are not allowed to claim their basic rights, including education, marriage, and employment. Juliet was forced to marry a man chosen by her father. The society considered men as the head of the family, and the whole family had to live their life according to him. Juliet is considered an object and has to face the primitive traditions, and their rights are deeply affected, which they accepted.

Every person has their own rights, and women have to be considered equal to men. They have the right to get an education, to make decisions, and to live their life according to their will. Women have the authority to make decisions. Juliet resisted these limitations and tried to delay her marriage and make excuses not to get married. Then she decided to break all these limits and boundaries which were set by male-dominated society and elope with Romeo, leave her family and drink the potion given by the friar and end her life. So, women should be considered as an equal part of society in (Sinta & Ambalegin, 2020).

Ahmed-Gosh (2003) elaborate about Afghanistan in which most the women are affected by primitive traditions in rural areas. Some women understand their rights and try to fight for them. But this is a small portion of women who belong to the elite class and become role models for those women who are suffering due to tribal traditions, and whose rights are suppressed. The change came when women from different classes tried to fight for their rights. The stability in the economy and politics came when men and women worked hard for the nation. If they want to become a democratic country, they need to understand women's rights, and they must be given the right to education, employment, marriage, and the right to make decisions that are appropriate for them. The situation of rights in Afghanistan needs a democratic change that leads to modernism, secularism, and gender equality. Women in Afghanistan are being objectified and suppressed, and are not allowed to go out of their homes. They would like to follow Western models, but they never gave importance to the rights of women. They provide a new example for hybridity. Society has to understand the importance of women's rights. They would not be able to blame Islam for their vulnerable state. They have to understand the circumstances today to make their own identity (Ahmed-Gosh, 2003).

Adhikary (2020) in his article illustrate about the Jan Smiley's *A Thousand Acres* (1991) has the basic purpose of describing women's rights, and they resist and show rebellion against the dehumanization of women through the authoritative structure. The character of Larry Cook's father becomes the reason for their dehumanization and disrespect of the family. He never gave importance to the rights of their daughter, and remained unlinked with them and always tried to run away from their responsibility, but the daughters took the initiative for the betterment and tried to fulfill their economic condition. He never gave respect to their daughters and always abused and exploited them morally and sexually, which became a trauma for them. Ginny tried to show resistance against all these exploitations. She tried to fight for their own rights and to get their identity and freedom. She was sexually abused by her own father and accused of mismanagement in the farm, which had a great impact on her mentality, and she became stronger through these circumstances and struggled hard for her own rights. Sometimes her sister helps her, but she has to become strong and brave against all these conditions; everyone believes in male dominance except Taylor, but Ginny's husband thought that a better patriarchal

system would not allow women to progress in their lives. So the marginalization, exploitation, and the dehumanization encourage Ginny to struggle for the rights, their own identity, and especially for their existence (Adhikary, 2020).

Azhar (2022) in his article explained about Ahmad Ali's *Twilight in Delhi* (1940) describes the silence and dependence of women. In this novel, women are suppressed, abused, and marginalized in a male-dominant society. It describes the types of females who are considered dancing girls and housewives. The woman is seen as an object and the male use them for their own purposes, they use dancing girls for their emotional and physical needs, and dehumanize them and are being marginalized, their rights are repressed and these women are considered as inferior and others .while the housewives like Begum Nihal always struggle hard and face hardships in order to provide happiness and peace to their husband. They tried hard to fulfil all of their needs because society put some limitations on them. The four walls of the house are used to hide all of the abuses and violence on the woman because they are pressured by society, and Bilqees and they tried hard to gain their identity for their existence. Men use women for their own purposes and consider them as static, like water in a pond with nothing to break the static life. Women are not allowed to make decisions regarding their lives, marriage, and especially decisions at home. The male is considered the head of the house, and women have to obey all of their orders. The rule of acceptance and to obey their males is ingrained in their blood since they are children. So, light in Delhi puts focus on the lives of women and their sufferings (Azhar, 2022).

3. Theoretical Framework

Chandra Talpade Mohanty's Transnational Feminism describes women's rights in a globalized era and investigates anti-imperialism and anti-capitalism. These theories describe feminism Without Borders and also explore decolonization. It finds out the experiences and struggles of women and their resistance against all these circumstances at a universal level. It merely describes women as third-world women, which includes problems and the experiences often described as single, not as Western or Eastern. It explores the differences in culture, social values, and political and economic context. It centers on Western feminism, which is regarded as superior due to its power and knowledge. This describes solidarity as gender with race, class, nation, and sexuality; all these affect their life, and they are oppressed in different ways. The women were not only suppressed because of their rights, but also due to environmental exploitation, and the privatization of Labor also had a great impact on their lives. All these things required transnational feminism at the level. Women have to be given equal rights and respect as men, and they should be given equal opportunities. It pays great attention to the development of the rights of women, which is globally shared, so feminism should be supported at the global level.

The Transnational Feminism by Chandra Talpade Mohanty overlaps with Post Colonialism, Third World Feminism, and Intersectionality. This theory criticizes the impact of imperialism and colonialism on the people, especially the rights of women, which are generally greatly suppressed due to an authoritative and patriarchal structure. This theory overlaps with third-world feminism and describes the issues of feminism at the capital level. This theory is connected with intersectionality, which considers that women's rights have been suppressed and violated due to race, color, gender, and sexuality. It further explores the social and political power dynamics that put limitations on women and cause an imbalance of rights. So this theory challenges the Western knowledge and local models about the dehumanization of women. It also studies the power dynamics and systems that place limitations on women across national and cultural borders. It promotes solidarity that expresses the rights at an equal level and resistance against the forces and resilience for their identity, especially for their existence. It further explores angles of reclaiming their identity and anti-essentialism, which portrays that women have to raise their voices against violence and engage in their struggle for rights and existence. These women have to show resistance against all the circumstances and also describe the Eurocentric theory and decolonization, which have been established pedagogies and practices for the rights across cultures.

Conway (2017) briefly describes the relationship between women and society for the struggle of their basic rights, which have been violated through centuries, and cultures play a double role in making their identity. First culture makes the identity of women and then puts limitations on their liberalism in the name of societal values and traditions. It further explores the relation of economy, society, and women's rights in the entire universe about the movement of Labor for women for the sustainable development Conway (2007). Falcón (2012) in this article explores transnational feminism and its connections with power, as both are interlinked. Transnational feminism further investigates the racism, sexism, and dehumanization of women at the local level and these are linked to the power dynamics.

4. Analysis and Discussion

This research explores how *Lion Women of Tehran* becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in the globalized world. It further explores the unification of women against this oppression and their struggle and resistance against the power dynamics that marginalize them on a global scale. This deals with the questions of oppression of women and their unification and resistance against the power dynamics at a global scale. It has been analyzed with Chandra Talpade Mohanty's Transnational Feminist perspective which discusses women's rights in a globalized era and investigates anti-imperialism and anti-capitalism. It finds out the experiences and struggles of women and their resistance against all these circumstances at a universal level.

The first research question discusses how the novel becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in a post-globalized world. This novel clearly describes the oppression of women through the characters of Homa and Ellie, who are best friends and whose rights were oppressed, and this novel became a way for these women to express their difficulties and hardships through literature. “When you see the women screaming in Iran for their rights, please remember, dear Leily, that the force and fury of our screams have been gathering power for years” (Kamali, 2024, p.311). These lines clearly describe the suppression of women not only in Iran but at the global level. The screaming of women portrays feminist awareness, and it became a movement across borders for the worldwide oppressed women, and their fury became a power of unity for them. So, this novel becomes a mouthpiece for those women who have been silenced for many centuries. Women who are living their life in a patriarchal and authoritative society need to make a change. The government policies make their existence impossible, and Kamali find out about the eradication of these policies.

And the marches we had, the tens of thousands who showed up, the screams we made heard, are all in vain. Hijab becomes mandatory. Improper hijab is punishable by fines, beatings, and even imprisonment. We have a new morality police. They patrol the streets looking for visible strands of hair (Kamali, 2024, p.220).

This clearly exposes the governmental control over women. The use of morality police is the result of the patriarchy, which is used under the disguise of tradition or in the name of moral values. All these steps are used to oppress the rights of women and their freedom, and these are the violations that need to be discussed at the global level, and they need to be removed, and gendered equality is important without hypocrisy in modern societies. Women have equal rights as men, and these limitations expose the institutionalized control over women.

Women protest for their basic rights, and their struggle has been introduced through the literature. As Homa protests against the Shah's policies and they have meetings in the garages to discuss their further steps against the government, but they were arrested and tortured, and even Homa was arrested and raped in prison. “Students like the one I used to be protested. We were arrested. Then released. Some were tortured and fined. Many were killed. We wanted freedom. Freedom of speech, of assembly” (Kamali, 2024, p.204). These lines clearly represent the personal pain of the students and of the other women like Homa have to face, and these women have to pay for their rights and liberation, and Kamali gives them an opportunity to describe their efforts, struggles, and the sacrifices for freedom and even for existence. It further relates their struggles to the transnational movement for justice and becomes a mouthpiece against that regime that needs to be erased.

The second question of this research is related to the unification of women against this oppression on a global scale. Kamali portrays the unification through Homa and Ellie, who are best friends and always dream of their future together and imagine the courage of a lioness to make their future bright and always dreamed of changing the world. As the novel describes “Someday, you and me-we’ll do great things. We’ll live life for ourselves. And we will help others. We are cubs now, maybe. But we will grow to be lionesses. Strong women who make things happen” (Kamali, 2024, p.38). Childhood dreams are the prophecy of empowerment and unity. The use of lioness is the symbol of strength, leadership, and communal courage. It describes the sisterhood and the bond among the worldwide women and became an inspiration against the oppression. This is a universal signal for the women's struggles and the sacrifices across the borders as Kamali represents them with “we,” and it is the sign of unification.

Their friendship and dreams do not only represent individuals, but they are linked in a world where women's voices were silenced, the characters' friendship became a beacon of hope and resistance around the world. Kamali represents the unification against the oppression through the characters when Homa began to protest against the policies, with her daughter Bahar, as a breaking point against the policies, and the other people began to connect with these women.

I am ready to protect Bahar and every woman in this march. And then. Before I could move, we were surrounded. Another group of men has made their way across the street and into the chaotic crowd. They come close to us and hold hands with one another. They form a human chain around us (Kamali, 2024, p.219).

These lines describe the women standing with each other to protect their rights and to get rid of patriarchal violence. The formation of a human chain is the symbol of unity, protection, and their resistance. It further explores that the empowerment came from the unification and courage, and this provides a way for worldwide marches of women, which shows the shared oppression and connection that develops in women globally. The unification against all these oppressions is greatly presented and struggle hard and unite for the rights of women in Iran and relate to the whole world.

Now, with the protests after Masha’s death and the country reverberating in grief, I feel the rage continuously. I feel it in every limb of my body, in every milliliter of my blood. Of course, I go out with the young women and men protesting night after night (Kamali, 2024, p. 310).

Masha's death is the collective awakening and unification in grief and defiance. The death became a catalyst for women across Iran to unite against inequality and injustice. Homa and Masha’s physical participation shows local pain into solidarity at the global level. Through this, Kamali connects the struggle of women at a broader level and gives a

way for women to fight for their rights and shows oppression as a shared burden and resistance is represented as a power.

The third question of this research is to determine how women resist the power dynamics that marginalized them. Kamali represents the resistance of women for their rights against the powers that tried to dehumanize and marginalize them as Homa show resistance against the institutionalized policies.

Let them beat me with their batons, let them bruise my body to a pulp, let them shoot and kill me. For a lifetime we have fought. We have fought and fought and fought. We want to be free. We want to be equal. We want to be able to live our lives (Kamali, 2024, p. 310).

This quote describes the resistance against the violence and oppression of women. The characters' struggle and resilience represents the moral victory of oppressed women against the authoritative and patriarchal structure. Kamali represents that physical subjugation and punishment cannot silence them for the demand of freedom and equality. These women fought for their rights and challenged the powers that tried to marginalize them. They demand equality and freedom to live a better life. All these things are symbols of resilience and fearless resistance. Kamali represents the true picture of Iranian society through the characters when Homa tried to give advice to her daughter to show struggle and resistance for their rights and fought against the power dynamics that dehumanize them. "This world is filled with liars and scoundrels who will do anything to take advantage of you. Do not let them . Do not let people take what is yours. Put yourself first. Promise me" (Kamali, 2024, p. 61). The description of put yourself first challenges the authoritative structure that teaches women to sacrifice their rights. Kamali describes resistance, which is self-worth and self-preservation, as more important for girls. This advice is seemingly quiet, but it is a rebellion against the authoritative system to ensure women's rights.

Kamali describes that the resistance that begins within itself describes joy and confidence. The rebellion against the structure for which women who sacrifices their dreams and their lives became a movement for women's rights. The women's resistance against all these circumstances, who have been silenced for generations in a patriarchal society. "Yours is a sycophantic cult of which my generation is ashamed. We want a better country. We want equality in all aspects. We want freedom. We want to live with dignity" (Kamali, 2024,p.164). Through this, Kamali represents the resistance of younger generations to show women's rejection of inherited obedience and the courage to break the silence into speech for freedom and liberation to live life according to their will. Through this novel, Kamali shows resistance against society as Homa shows resistance against the laws and Ellie shows resistance against the societal values and tries to speak for their rights.

They are tired of being told how to behave, what to say, what to wear, and whom to worship. Tired of their rights being diminished. Their slogan, born of a Kurdish fighting slogan, is “Women, Life, Freedom”. In Kurdish: “Jin, Jiyan, Azadi”. In Persian: “Zan, Zendagi, Azadi (Kamali, 2024, p.307).

These women show their resistance with the slogans of women, life, freedom, which collectively represent the resistance against these patriarchal structures, which are organized collectively and represent the women from the whole world that are living their lives in oppression and remain silenced through generations. The feminist struggle demands life, liberty and dignity without cultural and universal resonance, which shows resistance not only through protests but by creating movements for women's rights across borders. So, this is collective resistance against these power dynamics that marginalize women and their rights.

5. Discussion

The findings of this research describe the women’s resistance against patriarchal and authoritative structures at the global level and how this resistance is portrayed in the literature. The analysis of *Lion women of Tehran* describes the characters' challenge to the social and political oppression and their struggle hard for their rights of education, marriage, right to vote, and rights about divorce and children's custody. These women unified against this suppression and broke the silence against those power dynamics that marginalized them and struggled hard for their identity and even for their existence. These results align with previous studies that describe women's resistance, as in the novel, exploring Mukhtar Mai, who raises their voice against the violence and shows resistance against the authoritative structure in order to get their own rights, as described in Mu’arraf (2016).

This resistance is described by other work, like *The Bluest Eyes*, which describes the women's rights that are marginalized, and they have to face abuses and violence, as the characters like Pecola, Fredia, and Claudia have to face. Novel portrays about the power dynamics, oppression, and the societal traditions have a bad impact on their identity. It has been described that literature is used as a tool to describe the societal problems faced by women and a catalyst to change these assumptions, Madhavi & Rao (2023). So, Transnational Feminism by Chandra Talpade Mohanty also describes the women's resistance and their unification against the patriarchal structure at a global level.

This research includes a limited literary work from different regions, but it provides a new concept for future researchers to serve as a powerful space in political and societal resistance. So, they would be able to present women's resistance and unification for their own identity at a global level. In conclusion, the discussion reveals that women resist not only for freedom from authoritative structure but also for freedom within their own

societies. Their resistance symbolizes resilience, transformation, hope, and the reclaiming of their women's identity at a broader level.

6. Conclusion

To conclude, the novel *Lion women of Tehran* discuss about the marginalization of the women in Tehran and the oppression of their basic rights which are not given to the women. The aims and the objective of this research are that this novel becomes a mouthpiece against the oppression of women in the globalized world. It further explores the unification of women against this oppression and their struggle and resistance against the power dynamics that marginalize them on a global scale. This discusses the oppression of women and their unification and resistance against the power dynamics at a global scale. The theory which was applied on this novel was the Chandra Talpade Mohanty's Transnational Feminism describes women's rights in a globalized era and investigates anti-imperialism and anti-capitalism. These theories describe feminism Without Borders and also explore decolonization. It finds out the experiences and struggles of women and their resistance against all these circumstances at a universal level. Through this theory the rights of all the women were discussed at global level with hope and resistance.

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